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Influence of Globalization on Cargo Dwell Time and Ship Turnaround Time in Nigerian Ports

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ABSTRACT

The study investigated the influences of economic globalization on ship turnaround time and cargo dwell time in Nigerian seaports. The objectives of the study were among other things, to model the effects of economic globalization of ship turnaround time in Nigeria ports and to establish the relationship between globalization and cargo dwell time in Nigerian ports. The study used quantitative research design in which time series secondary data on ship turnaround time and cargo dwell time in Nigerian ports were sourced from the Nigeria Ports Authority while data on KOF trade and financial globalization index de facto and de jure were sourced from the International Monetary Fund. Each dataset covered a period of 15 years between 2005 and 2019. The log-linear multiple regression analysis method was used to analyse the data obtained. It was found that while there is significant effect of economic globalization on ship turnaround time in Nigerian ports while the relationship between globalization and the trend of cargo dwell time in Nigerian ports over the period is not significant. The following empirical models among others were developed showing the effects of economic globalization on the trend of ship turnaround time and cargo dwell time in Nigerian ports: $InSHIP_{turnaround\ time} = -3.412 + 2.114InKOFTRGIDf + 1.262InKOFTRGIDj - 0.602InKOFFGIDj - 1.415InKOFFGIDf$; $InCARGO_{dwell\ time} = 3.082 - 0.245InKOFTRGIDf - 0.187InKOFTRGIDj + 0.186InKOFFGIDj + 0.234InKOFFGIDf$. The policy implications were discussed and recommendations proffered in line with the study findings.

Keywords: *Economic-globalizations, effects, ship-turnaround time, cargo-dwell-time, port-logistics, Nigeria*

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1.0 INTRODUCTION

Several studies have argued in favour and against trade liberalization and globalization in weak economies and developing countries such as Nigeria (Czaika and Villares-Varela, 2017; Battini, Peretti, Persona & Sgarbossa, 2014). The proponents and supporters of trade liberalization and globalization argue that it encourages economic growth, wealth creation and economic development, consequent from the increased flow of trade in goods and services, foreign direct investment and foreign capital; brought about by the freedom of foreign nationals other than the citizens of the local country to invest in and trade in the reference country, for example, Nigeria (Adesina, 2012). Others viewed trade liberalization and globalization is a major cause of dumping in weak nations, death of local indigenous firms induced by unfavorable competition with foreign firms and the consequent loss of jobs and employment opportunities, capital flight caused by the repatriation of profits in hard currency by foreign firms, pressure on the inadequate infrastructure such as port facilities, rail and road infrastructure in weaker nations, with the associated costs, among many other disadvantages of the globalization and trade liberalization identified in available empirical literature. The implication is that, just as trade liberalization and globalization have beneficial effects as aforementioned, it also have negative impacts; so that at any given point in time, a developing country with weak economy should analyze the significance of the impacts of liberalization and globalization policies, and determine how best to curtail the negative impacts of globalization, given the significance of such impacts, before opening its doors to implementation of strategies that partially or wholly enhance trade globalization (Arrighi, 2005; Angel 2007)..

In Nigeria for example, the maritime sub-sector of the national economy is the fulcrum upon which other sectors of the economy depends. The maritime transport sub-sector in conjunction with the offshore oil and gas industry sub-sector is highest revenue contributor to the Federal government. Much foreign operators and foreign direct investment is witnessed in this sub-sector over the years, providing evidence of elements of globalizations in the maritime –sub-sector. However, the trade liberalization and globalization policies of government in this important sub-sector are still unclear and undefined. The dirt of indigenous shipping companies and ship operators, and poor performance of indigenous firms in international shipping import and export trade has been linked to the domination of the industry by both foreign operators and shippers (Aylin & Yucel, 2016). The basic problem is the seeming assumption by policy managers in the Nigeria maritime sector that trade liberalization and globalization in the sector has solely beneficial effects, thus attempt is not made to understand holistically the impacts of globalization on the output of the maritime sector and maritime logistics and the significance of such impacts so as to protect local operators in the maritime sector from the negative impacts of globalization. Given the increasing trend of cargo dwell time and ship turnaround time in Nigeria ports which has over the years led to increased trend of port cost to shippers, ship-owners and charterers, it is even more important to understand to what extent trade globalization has influenced cargo dwell time (time spent by shippers in port to get shipments processed for delivery to markets and warehouses) and ship turnaround time (time spent by ships in port to get loaded with cargo or discharged). Thus, there is a seeming lack of empirical information on the influences of trade globalization on cargo dwell time and ship turnaround time in Nigerian ports. This will form the basis for developing policies for the protection of local shipping industry and port sector from the negative effects of trade globalization in the Nigerian port logistics sub-sector. The port logistics sector in Nigeria as a component of the overall maritime logistics system faces pressure induced by trade globalization such that the Ship Turnaround Time (STRT), Cargo Dwell Time (CDT), port cost (port dues and charges), among other port logistics indices faces increasing trend over the years to the disadvantage of the overall economy (Nwokedi, Ndikom, Okoroji and Nwaorgu, 2021). The International Monetary Funds (IMF) according to Gygli, Florian, Niklas and Jan-Egbert (2019) uses the KOF globalization index which for economic globalization, comprised of:

- (i) KOF Trade Globalization de facto
- (ii) KOF Trade Globalization de jure,
- (iii) KOF Financial Globalization de facto and
- (iv) KOF Financial Globalization de jure, as indices for measuring the impacts of economic globalization on a given economy.

While trade globalization de facto is a measure of the exports and imports of goods in the economy as a percentage of the Gross Domestic Product (GDP), trade globalization de jure is a measure of the average prevalence of non-tariff trade barriers and compliance costs of importing and exporting as well as income from taxes on international trade as percentage of revenue (Gygli et al, 2019). Financial globalization de facto is a measure of the sum of stocks of assets and liabilities of foreign direct investments in the economy as a percentage of the GDP, sum of stocks of assets and liabilities of international equity portfolio investments as a percentage of the GDP and sum of inward and outward stocks of international portfolio debt securities and international bank loans and deposits as a percentage of the GDP. The financial globalization de jure is a measure of the capital account openness and number of Bilateral Investment Agreements (BITs) and Treaties with Investment Provisions (TIPs) in the economy, e.g. Nigeria.

It is important to assess the influence of globalization measured by trade globalization de facto, trade globalization de jure, financial globalization de facto and financial globalization de jure on the aforementioned port-logistics indices using the globalization index as measures (Nwokedi, Ndikom, Okoroji and Nwaorgu, 2021). These will provide empirical information and basis for developing policies and strategies to proactively influence trade liberalization and globalization and the benefit and development of the local shipping industry and port logistics sector in Nigeria

2.0 LITERATURE REVIEW

Ubam, and Wilcox (2017) did a review of the effects of globalization on Nigeria economic development. The study set out to understand the disposition of the Nigerian political leaders in developing the political will to break away from depending on the International Capitalist system whose interest is to perpetuate the country's peripheral status. It notes the failure of Nigeria to achieve sustainable development after serial implementation of strategies aimed at achieving such. It blamed such woeful failures on globalization and vested interest of foreign countries in perpetually benefiting substantially from Nigeria more than Nigerian (Ubam, and Wilcox, 2017). The study observes that notwithstanding the negative influences of globalization, Nigeria still pursue globalization policies vigorously in keeping with the demands of the International Financial Institution of the World Bank and International Monetary Fund (IMF). In view of this, the study investigated the effects of globalization on Nigeria's economy especially within the democratic dispensation. The findings of the study indicate that globalization has led to positive improvement in the trends of political, economic, social and technological development in Nigeria. It concludes that giving the drive towards a globally connected World and the becoming of a global village concept; the World is now deeply embedded in interdependency and Nigeria cannot afford to starve her economy of the impacts of globalization (Ubam, and Wilcox, 2017).. It however advocated that it is a necessity for Nigeria to minimize the negative effects of globalization while exploring its benefits for national development and economic growth (Ubam, and Wilcox, 2017).

Popoola (2020) in similar but separate study on 'globalization and Nigeria's economic development- a study of the interconnectedness'; investigated the interrelationship between economic development and globalization in Nigeria. The study used exploratory research design method, primary data obtained through survey and secondary data on indices of economic development to investigate the relationship between economic development in Nigeria and globalization (Popoola, 2020).. The result of the study indicates that there is a significant relationship between globalization and economic development in Nigeria. It also reveals that increase in the rate of globalization in Nigeria is partly responsible for the increasing rate of unemployment in Nigeria. It thus concluded that globalization is discovered to be the root cause of massive youth unemployment and lack of opportunities for growth among the youths in Nigeria. The findings of the study corroborates the findings of Ubam and Wilcox (2017) that while the developed countries benefit massively from globalization, growing/undeveloped countries tend to benefit less (Popoola, 2020).

A similar study by Dappa and Thom-otuya (2010) examines globalization and its effects on third World Economic development with emphasis on Nigerian economy. The study used a mixed

approach comprised of the use of both primary and secondary data to investigate the effects of globalization on third world countries using Nigeria as a case study. The study found that globalization induces unequal effects on nations, which has subsequently preponderantly distorted third world economic development. This has also led to its lack of infrastructure in every sector of the Nigerian economy, poverty, accompanied with its consummate terminal deceases, poor agricultural sector output, poor funding of the educational sector as the upper class migrate their children and wards to foreign Universities and colleges that are better funded. It also found that globalization has led to huge gap between the income per capita in the developed and third world countries such that income per capita in Nigeria has been on the downward trend with no meaningful result from policy changes. Inflation, unemployment, armed banditry and other vices continue to be on the increase, thereby inhibiting foreign trade investment. Globalization is also found to have influenced cultural values among Nigerian as the inherent cultural and social values, constitute major barriers to desired corresponding result in earnings (Dappa and Thom-otuya; 2010; Kumar, 2002).

Makinde (2013) appraised the effects of globalization on the Nigerian. The study employed the use of secondary data sourced from the Central Bank of Nigeria statistical bulletin and the National Bureau of Statistics between 1986 and 2011 using the Gross Domestic Product (GDP) to proxy the Nigerian economy as the dependent variables and the Foreign Direct Investment (FDI) into Nigeria cum Export and Import (foreign trade) data as the proxies for globalization are used as the explanatory variables. Using the Ordinary Least Square (OLS) multiple regression techniques as the analytical method; the study revealed that there is a strong positive relationship between the Nigerian Gross Domestic Product (GDP) and foreign Direct Investment (FDI). This implies that the FDI has impacted on the Nigerian economy positively (Makinde, 2013). The findings of the study also shows that import has been growing over time though not at the pace of the GDP, whereas exports shows significantly declining trend over the period. It recommended that Government should concentrate efforts towards creating an enabling environment for more inflow of FDI into the economy while the importation of products that are produced locally should be discouraged to enable export and local production to thrive (Makinde, 2013; Nwokah, 2015).

From the available empirical studies, it is observed that there exist a research gap on what extent trade globalization and liberalisation policies have influenced the trend of cargo dwell time and ship turnaround time in Nigeria ports. Available researches have failed to provide evidence on the empirical relationship that indicates the extent of effects of globalization on cargo dwell time and ship turnaround time in Nigeria ports. This is the knowledge gap which this study seeks to provide solution to.

3.0 DATA AND METHODS

The study used quantitative research approach in which time series (historical) data obtained from secondary sources were used for the study. The secondary data were sourced from the various sources including the International Monetary Fund (IMF), the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) Annual Statistical report, and the Nigeria Ports Authority (NPA) Statistical Reports among other sources. Data on the KOF globalization index for the Nigeria state was obtained from the International Monetary Fund (IMF). Data on the values of cargo dwell time and ship turnaround time in Nigeria ports over the years were obtained from the Nigeria Ports Authority (NPA). Each data set gathered from the study covered a period of 15 years from 2005 to 2019.

3.1 Method of Data Analysis: Log-Linear Multiple Regression

Using the Log-Linear multiple regression model approach, the influence of economic globalization on cargo dwell time and ship turnaround time in Nigeria seaports was estimated. The KOF economic globalization index was used to denote globalization. The KOF economic globalization index according to the IMF is further divided into four parts as listed below:

- (i) KOF trade globalisation de facto (KOFTrGldf),
- (ii) KOF trade globalisation de jure (KOFFiGldj)

- (iii) KOF financial globalization de factor (KOFFiGIdf)
- (iv) KOF financial globalization de jure (KOFFiGIdj)

The effects of the each of the four identified indices of economic globalization above on each of cargo time(CARGO_{dwelltime}) and ship turnaround time(SHP_{turnroundtime}) in Nigeria port were estimated.

where:

- (i) Trade globalization, de facto (KOFTrGIdf)
- (ii) Trade globalization, de jure (KOFTrGIdj)
- (iii) Financial globalization, de facto (KOFFiGIdf)
- (iv) Financial globalization, de jure (KOFFiGIdj)

Having identified in line with the objectives of the study the relationships to be estimated and the associated variables of the study we specified the models of the study as shown below:

3.2 Model Specification

$$SHP_{turnroundtime} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 KOFTrGIdf + \beta_2 KOFTrGIdj + \beta_3 KOFFiGIdf + \beta_4 KOFFiGIdj \quad (1)$$

$$CARGO_{dwelltime} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 KOFTrGIdf + \beta_2 KOFTrGIdj + \beta_3 KOFFiGIdf + \beta_4 KOFFiGIdj \quad (2)$$

Ordinary least square estimation can be used to estimate the effects of each economic globalization variable on the variables of maritime trade and logistics. However, to ensure that all variables of the study assume the same unit of measurement, we took the natural log (ln) of each set of data and used the Log-linear multiple regression analysis method to analyze the data obtained. The above models are re-expressed in log-linear regression model formats as shown below:

$$\ln SHP_{turnroundtime} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \ln KOFTrGIdf + \beta_2 \ln KOFTrGIdj + \beta_3 \ln KOFFiGIdf + \beta_4 \ln KOFFiGIdj \quad (3)$$

$$\ln CARGO_{dwelltime} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \ln KOFTrGIdf + \beta_2 \ln KOFTrGIdj + \beta_3 \ln KOFFiGIdf + \beta_4 \ln KOFFiGIdj \quad (4)$$

Using the methods discussed above, the study analyzed the data obtained in order to provide answers to the research questions. They hypotheses were also tested using the t-test corresponding to the log-linear multiple regression estimates of each of the above relationships.

4.0 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

Table-1: Descriptive Statistics showing the values of economic globalization index for Nigeria between 2005 and 2019

	N	Range	Minimum	Maximum	Sum
	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic
KOFTRGDF	15	10.00	42.00	52.00	682.00
KOFTRGDJ	15	8.00	49.00	57.00	767.00
KOFFGDJ	15	14.00	28.00	42.00	553.00
KOFFGDF	15	14.00	51.00	65.00	864.00
Valid N (listwise)	15				

Descriptive Statistics

	Mean		Std. Deviation
	Statistic	Std. Error	Statistic
KOFTRGIDF	45.4667	.86115	3.33524
KOFTRGIDJ	51.1333	.55948	2.16685
KOFFGIDJ	36.8667	1.17865	4.56488
KOFFGIDF	57.6000	.96016	3.71868
Valid N (listwise)			

Source: Authors calculation

Table-1 above shows that the mean values of economic globalization index for Nigeria measured by the KOF trade globalization de facto (KOFTRGIDF), trade globalization de jure (KOFTRGIDJ), financial globalization de facto (KOFFGIDF) and financial globalization de jure (KOFFGIDJ) for Nigeria between 2005 and 2019 is 45.4667, 51.1333, 57.6000, and 36.8667 for trade globalization de facto, trade globalization de jure, financial globalization de facto, and financial globalization de jure respectively with respective standard deviations of 0.86115, 0.55948, 0.96016 and 1.17865. By implication, KOF financial globalization de facto, which measures the level of foreign direct investment, Portfolio investment, international equity portfolio investments and International income payments has the highest mean score per annum between 2005 and 2019 of 57.600 among the four variables of economic globalization. This is seconded by KOF trade globalization de jure with mean score of 51.1333.

The range indicates the differences between the maximum and minimum values of each of the proxies used to identify maritime trade and economic globalization.

Table-2: Descriptive statistics of Cargo Dwell Time and Ship turnaround Time in Nigerian Ports between 2005 and 2019

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Sum	Mean	Std. Deviation
TURNROUNDTIME	15	3.90	10.05	86.29	5.7527	1.66481
DWELLTIME	15	18.00	24.00	311.00	20.7333	1.70992
Valid N (listwise)	15					

Source: Authors calculation

The result on Table-2 indicates that given the trend of economic globalization in Nigeria, the average values ship turnaround time and cargo dwell time in Nigeria ports per annum between 2005 and 2019 is 5.75days and 20.73days respectively with respective standard deviations of 1.665 and 1.7099.

Table-3: The influence of globalization on the trend of ship-turnaround time in Nigeria ports

	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
InSHIP _{turnroundtime}	1.7143	.26970	15
InKOFTRGIDf	3.8145	.07277	15
InKOFTRGIDj	3.9336	.04132	15
InKOFFGIDj	3.5995	.13225	15
InKOFFGIDf	4.0516	.06434	15

Model Summary^b

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson
1	.744 ^a	.554	.375	.21321	2.240

ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	.564	4	.141	3.100	.067 ^b
	Residual	.455	10	.045		
	Total	1.018	14			

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	Correlations
		B	Std. Error	Beta			Zero-order
1	(Constant)	-3.412	8.463		-.403	.695	
	InKOFTRGIDf	2.114	.828	.570	2.552	.029	.664
	InKOFTRGIDj	1.262	1.547	.193	.815	.434	.242
	InKOFFGIDj	-.602	.529	-.295	-1.136	.282	-.168
	InKOFFGIDf	-1.415	1.141	-.338	-1.240	.243	-.232

Residuals Statistics^a

	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
Predicted Value	1.4181	1.9734	1.7143	.20066	15
Residual	-.40065	.34908	.00000	.18020	15
Std. Predicted Value	-1.477	1.291	.000	1.000	15
Std. Residual	-1.879	1.637	.000	.845	15

a. Dependent Variable: *InSHIP_{turnroundtime}*

Source: author's calculation

Table-3 above shows the result of the estimates of the influence of economic globalization on the trend of ship turnaround time in Nigeria seaports. It indicates that the coefficient of correlation R which measures the degree of correlation between ship turnaround time in Nigeria ports and economic globalization in Nigeria is 0.744. This implies that there is about 75% correlation between the trend of ship turnaround time in Nigeria ports and economic globalization measured by the KOF economic globalization index- trade globalization de facto, trade globalization de jure, financial globalization de facto and financial globalization de jure.

The equation of the relationship depicting the influence of economic globalization measured by the KOF economic globalization index- trade globalization de facto, trade globalization de jure, financial globalization de facto and financial globalization de jure on the trend of ship turnaround time in Nigeria ports is:

$$InSHIP_{turnroundtime} = -3.412 + 2.114InKOFTRGIDf + 1.262InKOFTRGIDj - 0.602InKOFFGIDj - 1.415InKOFFGIDf \quad (5)$$

This implies that a unit annual increase in KOF trade globalization de facto, such as trade in goods, trade in services leads to increase the trend of ship turnaround time in Nigeria ports by 2.114units. A unit increase in KOF trade globalization de jure causes about 1.262units increase in the ship

turnaround time in Nigeria seaports.

Similarly, a unit annual increase in KOF financial globalization index de jure causes a decrease of about 0.602units in the ship turnaround time in Nigeria ports while a unit increase in KOF financial globalization index de facto such as a foreign direct investment inflow into Nigeria induces a 1.415units decrease in the ship turnaround time in Nigeria ports.

The coefficient of determination r^2 which measures the explanatory power of the model is 0.554. This indicates that about 55% variation in the trend of ship turnaround time in Nigeria ports is explained by economic globalization.

Table-4: The relationship between economic globalization and cargo dwell time in Nigeria ports

	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
InDWELL _{time}	3.0286	.08181	15
InKOFTRGIDf	3.8145	.07277	15
InKOFTRGIDj	3.9336	.04132	15
InKOFFGIDj	3.5995	.13225	15
InKOFFGIDf	4.0516	.06434	15

Model Summary^b

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson
1	.385 ^a	.148	-.193	.08935	1.407

ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	.014	4	.003	.434	.781 ^b
	Residual	.080	10	.008		
	Total	.094	14			

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	Correlations
		B	Std. Error	Beta			Zero-order
1	(Constant)	3.082	3.546		.869	.405	
	InKOFTRGIDf	-.245	.347	-.218	-.706	.496	-.265
	InKOFTRGIDj	-.187	.648	-.095	-.289	.779	-.161
	InKOFFGIDj	.186	.222	.301	.839	.421	.230
	InKOFFGIDf	.234	.478	.184	.489	.635	.032

a. Dependent Variable: InDWELL_{time}

Source: author's calculation

Table-4 above shows the result of the estimates of the relationship between economic globalization on the trend of cargo dwell time prevailing in in Nigeria seaports. It indicates that the coefficient of correlation R which measures the degree of correlation between ship turnaround time in Nigeria ports and economic globalization in Nigeria is 0.385. This implies that there is very poor/weak positive correlation between the trend of cargo dwell time in Nigeria ports and economic globalization measured by the KOF economic globalization index- trade globalization de facto, trade globalization de jure, financial globalization de facto and financial globalization de jure.

The equation of the relationship depicting the influence of economic globalization measured by the KOF economic globalization index- trade globalization de facto, trade globalization de jure, financial globalization de facto and financial globalization de jure on the trend of cargo dwell time in Nigeria ports is:

$$InCARGO_{dwell-time} = 3.082 - 0.245InKOFTRGIDf - 0.187InKOFTRGIDj + 0.186InKOFFGIDj + 0.234InKOFFGIDf \quad (6)$$

This implies that a unit annual increase in KOF trade globalization de facto, such as trade in goods, trade in services leads to decrease the trend of cargo dwell time in Nigeria ports by 0.245units. A unit increase in KOF trade globalization de jure causes about 0.1872units decrease in the cargo dwell time in Nigeria seaports.

Similarly, a unit annual increase in KOF financial globalization index de jure causes a increase of about 0.186units in the cargo dwell time in Nigeria ports while a unit increase in KOF financial globalization index de facto such as a foreign direct investment inflow into Nigeria induces a 0.234units increase in the cargo dwell time in Nigeria ports.

The coefficient of determination r^2 which measures the explanatory power of the model is 0.148. This indicates that only about 15% variation in the trend of cargo dwell time in Nigeria ports is explained by economic globalization. The implication is that the port authorities have not implemented adequate maritime logistics measures to achieve significant reduction in cargo dwell time in the ports.

Table-5: Test of H_{05} : There is the no significant influence of economic globalization on trend of ship turnaround time in Nigeria ports

Hypotheses	F-cal.	F-critical	p-value/sig.	Decision
H_{05}	3.100	3.68	0.067	Accept H_{05}
Variable	t-cal.	t-critical	p-value/sig.	Decision
InKOFTRGIDf	2.552	1.75	.029	Reject H_{02}
InKOFTRGIDj	.815	1.75	.434	Reject H_{03}
InKOFFGIDj	-1.136	1.75	.282	
InKOFFGIDf	-1.240	1.75	.243	

Source: Authors calculation. Reject null hypotheses if $F\text{-cal} > f\text{-critical}$; Accept null hypotheses if $F\text{-cal.} < F\text{-critical}$

The test of hypothesis H_{05} shown in table-5 shows F-score of 0.434, F-critical of 3.68, and p-value of 0.067. Since F-score is less than F-critical, ($3.100 < 3.68$), we accept null hypothesis H_{05} . We conclude that there no significant effect of economic globalization on ship turnaround time in Nigeria between 2005 and 2019

Similarly, t-test was conducted to investigate the significance of the individual effects of trade globalization index de facto, trade globalization index de jure, financial globalization index de fact and financial globalization index de jure on the trend of ship turnaround time in Nigeria ports over the 15 years covered in the study. The result shows that only KOF trade globalization index de facto with t-cal. of 2.552 and t-critical of 1.75 and p-value of 0.029 have significant influence on the trend of ship turnaround time in Nigeria ports. This is because $2.552 > 1.75$.

The KOF financial globalization index de facto, KOF trade globalization index de jure and KOF financial globalization index de jure all have t-cal. less than the t-critical (i.e.: $0.815 < 1.75$; $1.136 < 1.75$; and $1.240 < 1.75$). The KOF financial globalization index de facto, KOF trade globalization index de facto and KOF financial globalization index de jure all have no significant effects on the trend of ship turnaround time in the ports over the period covered in the study.

Table-6: Test of H_{06} : Is there significant relationship between globalization and trend of cargo dwell time in Nigeria ports

Hypotheses	F-cal.	F-critical	p-value/sig.	Decision
H_{06}	0.434	3.68	.781 ^b	Reject H_{06}
Variable	t-cal.	t-critical	p-value/sig.	Decision
InKOFTRGIDf	-0.706	1.75	0.496	Reject H_{02}
InKOFTRGIDj	-0.289	1.75	0.779	Reject H_{03}
InKOFFGIDj	0.839	1.75	0.421	
InKOFFGIDf	0.489	1.75	0.635	

Source: Authors calculation. Reject null hypotheses if $F\text{-cal} > f\text{-critical}$; Reject null hypotheses if $F\text{-cal} < F\text{-critical}$

The test of hypothesis H_{06} shown in table-6 shows F-score of 0.434, F-critical of 3.68, and p-value of 0.781. Since F-score is less than F-critical, (0.434<3.68), we accept null hypothesis H_{06} . We conclude that there no significant effect of economic globalization on cargo dwell time in Nigeria between 2005 and 2019.

Similarly, t-test was conducted to investigate the significance of the individual effects of trade globalization index de facto, trade globalization index de jure, financial globalization index de fact and financial globalization index de jure on the trend of cargo dwell time in Nigeria ports over the 15 years covered in the study. The result shows that none of KOF trade globalization index de facto, KOF financial globalization index de facto, KOF trade globalization index de jure and KOF financial globalization index de jure have t-cal. greater than 1.75 (i.e.: 0.706<1.75; 0.289<1.75; 0.839<1.75; and 0.489<1.75).

5.0 CONCLUSION

The result of the study indicates that while there is significant effect of globalization on ship turnaround time in Nigerian ports, globalization has no significant effect on cargo dwell time in Nigerian seaports. However, the findings of the study reveals further that only KOF trade globalization index de facto with t-cal. of 2.552 and t-critical of 1.75 and p-value of 0.029 have significant influence on the trend of ship turnaround time in Nigeria ports. The KOF trade globalization index de facto, KOF financial globalization index de facto, KOF trade globalization index de jure and KOF financial globalization index de jure have t-cal. less than 1.75 (i.e.: 0.706<1.75; 0.289<1.75; 0.839<1.75; and 0.489<1.75).

The findings of the study also reveal that there no significant effect of economic globalization on cargo dwell time in Nigeria between 2005 and 2019. The t-test conducted to investigate the significance of the individual effects of trade globalization index de facto, trade globalization index de jure, financial globalization index de fact and financial globalization index de jure on the trend of cargo dwell time in Nigeria ports over the 15 years covered in the study reveal that none of KOF trade globalization index de facto, KOF financial globalization index de facto, KOF trade globalization index de jure and KOF financial globalization index de jure have t-cal. greater than 1.75 (i.e.: 0.706<1.75; 0.289<1.75; 0.839<1.75; and 0.489<1.75).

6.0 RECOMMENDATIONS

It is recommended among other things, in line with the findings of the study that:

1. The result of the study indicates that there is no significant effect of economic globalization on ship turnaround time in Nigeria ports. This indicates that the long ship turnaround time experience in Nigeria ports is as a result of port logistical planning and not pressure from economic globalization effects. The port authorities in all ports should therefore implement more efficient logistical plans in ports in order to reverse the long ship turnaround time in Nigeria ports.
2. Then result also indicates that there is no significant effect of economic globalization on cargo dwell time in Nigeria ports. This also implies that the long cargo dwell time in Nigeria ports is a result of poor logistical planning. Port authorities should therefore implement more efficient port planning and logistics systems to reverse the long cargo dwell time in Nigeria ports.

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